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Research Article

**ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NATURAL
COMPOUNDS FROM LIQUORICE****Dr. Sejal.G. Patel^{1*}, Dr. Rakesh jat², Dr.Hiren .R.Chaudhary³**¹ Department of Pharmacognosy, Nootan Pharmacy College, Visnagar, Gujarat, India.
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hrc_999@yahoo.co.in,Mobile Phone:+91-9427012388**Abstract:**

The present research work is mainly concened with the natural compounds that are obtained from traditional medicinal plants. There are number of natural compounds have been available in the nature. Some natural compounds are very useful to human being and have life pontential to save human from many incurable disease. Keeping view in the mind the research is focused to extract and isolate antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antihyperlipidmic, antidiabetic, antiulcer activites containing compounds are studied. The major natural compounds are liquorice, ginger, alliuam, triphala (harda, bahera, pipali, amla and guggulu). The glycyrrhyza glabra is obtained from rhizomes of liquorice and usefull as expectorant and ulcer healing properties with carbenoloxolone as major constituents. All components are isolated from the concerned extracts. The extractions of all plants are based on successive solvent extraction method for all drugs. The constituents are confirmed by structure elucidation. The structure of each compounds are intrepereted by different spectral techniques like Infrared spectrum, nuclear magnetic spectrum (hydrogen anc carbon thirteen spectra) and mass spectroscopy for moleculural formula and molecular weight of the unknown compounds.

Key words: *Liquorice, extraction and chromatography***Corresponding author:****Dr. Sejal.G. Patel,**

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INTRODUCTION:**Natural compounds**

Natural compounds are obtained in the nature from different medicinal and herbal plants. These are generally secondary metabolites of the various plant parts or waste compound of plant. These are obtained various parts of the herbs, shrubs or plants like stem, root, leaves, fruits, seeds, barks, rhizomes, flowers and entire plants. The particular part of the plant is collected, extracted and isolated for the collection of various types of natural compounds. We include alkaloids, glycosides, terpenoids, resins, tannins, carbohydrates, gums and exudates, lignans. These obtained drugs have various types of pharmacological and therapeutic application[1-6].

Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza*, Mulethi): liquorice consists of dried, peeled or unpeeled, root & stolon of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* belonging to family Leguminosae. It is also obtained from other species of *glycyrrhiza*, giving a drug with sweet taste. Liquorice have water soluble extractive not less than 20% w/w. On addition of 80% sulphuric acid, the thick section of drug or powder shows deep yellow color. Liquorice owes most of its sweet taste to glycyrrhine, the potassium & calcium salts of glycyrrhineic acid. The yellow color of liquorice is due to flavonoids. Carbenoxolone is used for ulcer healing as protective base[7-16].

Glycyrrhiza Glabra Plant; Inset:
Rhizome and roots

Taxonomy of Plant (Liquorice)

Botanical Name – *Glycyrrhiza glabra*
 Kingdom - Planate – Plants
 Subkingdom - Tracheobionta - Vascular plants
 Super division - Spermatophyta - Seed plants
 Genus - *Glycyrrhiza* - Liquorice
 Division - Magnoliophyta - Flowering plants
 Subclass - Rosidae
 Order - Fabales
 Family - Leguminosae/Fabaceae - Pea Family
 Species - *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.
 Cultivated Liquorice

Common Name – Liquorice, Liquorice (English), Lacleche (German), Reglisse (French), Regolizia (Italian), Kanzoh (Japanese), Gancao (Chinese), Yasti-madhu in Ayurveda & Mulethi (Hindi).

Phytochemistry:

Major Saponin: Glycyrrhizic acid is the major triterpenoid saponin (4–20%) in Liquorice rhizome & is used as a tool for recognizing the herb.

Minor Sapogenins: About fifty other sapogenins have been isolated from *Glycyrrhiza* species. *G. glabra* have 13 minor sapogenins, liquoric acid is found in high amount as compare to other minor sapogenins, these are glabrolide, 11-deoxyglabrolide, liquiritic acid, isoglabrolide, 11-deoxyglycyrrhithic acid, glycyrritol, 24-hydroxyglycyrrhetic acid, 24-hydroxy-11-deoxyglycyrrhithic acid, liquiritidolic acid etc [17-25].

EXPERIMENTAL:**General**

Pure marker compounds were isolated by using various chromatographic & their structures were determined based on various spectroscopic techniques as mentioned below.

Thin layer chromatography: Chromatographic reactions were monitored on analytical TLC (MERCCK TLC Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄) precoated plates. TLC plates were developed in CAMAG glass twin trough chamber (20 × 10 cm). TLC chromatograms were visualized by: (a) UV Detection Chamber at 254nm, (b) UV Detection Chamber at 366 nm (CAMAG) & (c) derivatizing TLC plates with 0.5% anisaldehyde in 5% sulphuric acid & charring them at high temperature (80-100 °C) in a hot air oven.

Column chromatography: Column chromatography was performed by using silica gel (60-120 mesh), followed by purification with silica gel (100-200 or 200-400 mesh) column or with Sephadex LH-20 (size exclusion chromatography).

Spectroscopic techniques: For establishing the chemical structure of pure marker compounds & their derivatives, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, DEPT & COSY experiments were performed on the BRUKER AVANCE 200, 400, & 500 MHz instrument with tetra methyl silane (TMS) as an internal standard. Chemical shift was given in δ -ppm value. Electro spray mass (ES-MS) spectra were recorded on HP-1100 MSD instrument.

Dictionary of Natural Compounds: (CRC, Chapman & Hall, London, 2011) isolated compounds were dereplicated & identified based on their report available in DNP & some compounds were identified by comparison (TLC, CO-TLC, ^1H -NMR, MS) with authentic samples[26-28].

Plant material

The rhizome of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* plant was collected from botany department of Indian Institute of Integrated Medicine (IIIM), Jammu. The plant was identified & authenticated by botanist, Dr. S.N. Sharma, Department of Taxonomy, IIIM, and Jammu. A voucher specimen is held in the institutional Herbarium.

Extraction & Isolation of Marker compounds from *G. glabra*

Extraction: 1 kg Powdered rhizomes were extracted with 1 L ethanol with mechanical stirring at room temperature this process repeated for 4 times for complete extraction. Then this extract was filtered &

concentrated under vacuum (175 mbar) at 40°C by using Rota vapor to provide crude extract (300 g).

Isolation of marker compounds: A neat & dried glass column was taken. A cotton plug was put at the base of the column & packed with silica gel (60-120 mesh, 1100 g). Then the extract (250 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of chloroform-methanol & it was mixed with 500 g silica gel (60-120 mesh) for slurry & charged into the column.

Column Specifications

Column Diameter	10 cm
Length of column	150 cm
Silica gel (60-120)	1100 g
Bed Length	35 cm

The column was eluted with step gradient solvent system of hexane-chloroform-ethyl acetate-methanol & water & 215 fractions were collected (100 ml each). All fractions were pooled on the basis of TLC & divided into 5 parts (Hexane fr-1 to 10, Chloroform fr-11 to 80, Ethyl acetate fr-81 to 180, Methanol fr-181 to 210 & Water fr-211 to 215) & then concentrated under high vacuum. All the fractions were then individually subjected to Column chromatography (Silica Gel 100-200 mesh) & Sephadex (LH-20) to isolate pure compounds as represented[29-35]

Identification of isolated compounds was carried out by comparison of spectral data & physical data with the reported data.

Fig1: Extraction & Isolation Protocol.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:**Characterization of marker compound.****1. Compound GG-09 (Hispaglabridin A)****Structure of Hispaglabridin-A**

Colourless needle shaped crystalline compound (25 mg) isolated from ethyl acetate fraction using silica gel (100-200 mesh) column chromatography & Sephadex (LH-20). It was eluted in 50% of ethyl acetate in hexane from silica gel column & then purified by LH-20 using methanol as eluting solvent. It was then recrystallized using cyclohexane. The structure of compound GG-09 was characterized as Hispaglabridin by comparison of its spectral data with reported data.

TLC: $R_F = 0.40$, Hexane: Ethyl acetate (30: 70), Visualization: UV-254 nm.

M.P. = 130-135 °C

¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 1.45 (6H, br s, (CH₃)₂-6''), 1.78 (3H, s, CH₃-5''), 1.84 (3H, s, H-4''), 2.85 (1H, dd, $J = 3.5$ Hz, H-2), 2.96 (1H, dd, $J = 10$ Hz, H-2), 3.40-3.47 (1H, m, H-3), 3.49 (2H, br d, $J = 7$ Hz, H-1''), 4.02 (1H, t, $J = 10.5$ Hz, H-4), 4.34 (1H, br dd, $J = 10$ Hz, H-4), 5.25 (1H, s, OH-2'), 5.27 (1H, br t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, H-2''), 5.59 (1H, d, $J = 10$ Hz, H-5'), 6.28 (1H, d, $J = 8$ Hz, H-6), 6.39 (1H, d, $J = 8$ Hz, H-5), 6.64 (1H, d, $J = 9.9$ Hz, H-4''), 6.79 (2H, d, $J = 8$ Hz, H-5'', 6'').

¹³C-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): 17.8 (C-5''), 22.8 (C-1''), 25.8 (C-4''), 27.6 (C-6a''), 27.7 (C-6b''), 31.0 (C-4), 31.7 (C-3), 70.1 (C-2), 75.9 (C-6''), 107.4 (C-6), 108.0 (C-5), 109.5 (C-4a), 114.3 (C-8), 114.6 (C-3'), 116.6 (C-5''), 121.4 (C-1'), 122.1 (C-2''), 126.9 (C-5), 127.6 (C-4''), 129.2 (C-6), 134.2 (C-3''), 150.2 (C-7), 151.5 (C-4), 152.4 (C-2), 153.6 (C-8a).

MS-ES: (Negative) m/z 391 [M-H]⁻ so the mass of the compound m/z 392 [M]⁻ corresponded to molecular formula (MW.-392.13).

Fig 2: ¹H-NMR of Hispaglabridin-A

Name of atom	Chemical shift	Interpretation
Ar hydrogen	6-8.2 p.p.m	neighboring group effect
Aliphatic hydrogen	2-3.2 ppm	splitting of signal
Vinyl group hydrogen	3.5-4 ppm	intensity is fast
Hydroxyl group hydrogen	2.1-2.5 ppm	number of signal
Epoxide hydrogen	2.3-2.4 ppm	nil
Methyl group	1.2-1.5 p.p.m	primary hydrogen

On the basis of hydrogen nuclear magnetic spectral the compound has aromatic and aliphatic hydrogen that are identified on the basis of chemical shift value in parts per million. The vinyl hydrogen has different chemical shift value. The methyl group contains primary hydrogen with minimum chemical shift value in parts per million. The epoxide shows different part per million ppm value of chemical shift.

On the basis of deuterium 2 nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum ($^2\text{D NMR}$) the compound has aromatic and aliphatic deuterium that are identified on the basis of chemical shift value in parts per million. The vinyl deuterium has different chemical shift

value. The methyl group contains primary deuterium with minimum chemical shift value in parts per million. The epoxide shows different part per million values of chemical shift.

ES-MS

Fig 5: ES-MS of Hispaglabridin-A

Mass Spectrum of Hispaglabridin A

On the given spectra of mol. mass we can determine the molecular wt of the compound. We know that the molecular ion peak gives the mass or molecular weight of the unknown compounds. In the given figure the base peak shows the peak at 394.876 that is the mass of the product. The parent peak is known as mass or molecular weight of the compound. The fragmentations of the compounds shows breaking points and metabolic products of the compounds that is very helpful for structure elucidation of the

compounds. The $m+1$, $m+2$, $m+3$ etc. Peaks are known as isotopic peak of the compound. These peaks are very helpful to determine the molecular formula of the unknown compounds. These two things molecular weight and molecular formula are very important determinant of the structural elucidation of the unknown compound. We represent relative intensity or abundance on the y-axis and molecular mass on the x-axis for interpretation [36-43].

12. Compound GG-47 (Glycyrrhetic acid)

Structure of Glycyrrhetic acid

1. T: Test Compound; 2. Co: Co-Spotting; 3. ST: Standard

Derivatized with AS reagent

100 mg Glycyrrhine was dissolved in 5 ml methanol & it was added to 5% HCl in a 50 ml round bottle flask. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h. at 100 °C. Reaction was monitored by TLC, after completion of reaction, it was concentrated to evaporate methanol & portioned with ethyl acetate (50 ml x 3), ethyl acetate portion was dried over sodium sulfate, & concentrated to get 50 mg colorless amorphous compound GG-47 which was identified as Glycyrrhetic acid by H-NMR & Mass spectroscopy.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, MeOD): δ(ppm) 0.72 (3H, s, H-3), 0.78 (3H, s, H-3), 0.91 (3H, s, H-3), 1.02 (6H, s, H-3), 1.06 (3H, s, H), 1.31 (3H, s, H-29), 3.16 (1H, dd, *J* = 11.8, 4.2 Hz, H-3), 5.58 (1H, s, H-12).

MS-ES: At (Negative) mode *m/z* 469 [M-H]⁻ & in (Positive) mode the *m/z* 471 [M+H]⁺ so the *m/z* 470 [M]⁺ corresponded with molecular formula C₃₀H₄₆O₄ (MW.- 470.32).

GG-47 (Glycyrrhetic acid)

¹H NMR

4.3

Fig 6: ¹H-NMR of Glycyrrhetic acid

Name of atom	Chemical shift	Interpretation
Vinyl group hydrogen	3.5-4 ppm	intensity is fast
Hydroxyl group hydrogen	2.1-2.5 ppm	number of signal
Methyl group	1.2-1.5 ppm	primary hydrogen
On the basis of hydrogen nuclear magnetic resonance NMR spectrum the compound has aromatic and aliphatic hydrogen that are identified on the basis of chemical shift value in parts per million. The vinyl hydrogen has different chemical shift value. The		methyl group contains primary hydrogen with minimum chemical shift value in parts per million. The epoxide shows different part per million values of chemical shift.

GG-47 (Glycyrrhetic acid)**ES-MS****Fig 7: ES-MS of Glycyrrhetic acid****Mass Spectra of Glycyrrhyhic acid**

Basis of molecular mass we can determine the molecular weight of unknown of the compound. We know that the molecular ion peak provides the mass or molecular weight of the unknown compounds. In the given figure the base peak shows the peak at 587.143 that is the mass of the product. The parent peak is known as mass or molecular weight of the compound. The fragmentations of the compounds show breaking points and metabolites of the compounds that is very helpful for structure

GG-33 (Formononetin)

elucidation of the compounds. The $m+1$, $m+2$, $m+3$ etc. Peaks are known as isotopic peak of the compound. These peaks are very helpful to determine the molecular formula of the unknown compounds. These two things molecular weight & molecular formula are very important determinant of the structural elucidation of the unknown compound. We represent relative intensity or abundance on the y-axis and molecular mass on the x-axis for interpretation.

 $^1\text{H NMR}$

Fig 8: ¹H-NMR of Formononetin

Name of atom	Chemical shift	Interpretation
-C6H3- hydrogen	6-8.5 ppm	neighboring group effect
Aliphatic hydrogen	2-3.2 p.p.m	splitting of signal
Vinyl group hydrogen	3.5-4 ppm	intensity is fast
Hydroxyl group hydrogen	2.1-2.5 p.p.m	number of signal
Epoxide hydrogen	2.3-2.4 ppm	nil
Methyl group	1.2-1.5 ppm	primary hydrogen

On the premise of 2D atomic attractive range (2D NMR) the compound has sweet-smelling and aliphatic deuterium that are distinguished on the premise of substance move an incentive in parts for each million. The vinyl deuterium has distinctive ¹H NMR (Expection)

substance move esteem. The methyl assemble contains primary deuterium with least synthetic move an incentive in parts for every million. The epoxide indicates diverse part per million estimation of compound move.

Fig 9: ¹H-NMR(exaption) of Formononetin

Name of atom	Chemical shift	Interpretation
Aroma. hydrogen	6-8.5 p.p.m	neighboring group effect
Aliphatic hydrogen	2-3.2 ppm	splitting of signal
Vinyl group hydrogen	3.5-4 ppm	intensity is fast
Hydroxyl group hydrogen	2.1-2.5 ppm	number of signal
Epoxide hydrogen	2.3-2.4 ppm	nearby proton
Methyl group	1.2-1.5 ppm	primary hydrogen

On the premise of hydrogen atomic attractive spectra the compound has fragrant and aliphatic hydrogen that are distinguished on the premise of concoction move an incentive in parts for every million. The vinyl hydrogen has distinctive substance move **GG-33 (Formononetin)**

esteem. The methyl aggregate contains essential hydrogen with least concoction move an incentive in parts for every million. The epoxide indicates distinctive part per million estimation of synthetic move.

¹³C NMR

Fig 10: ¹³C-NMR of Formononetin

Names of Atom

Aromatic carbons

Aliphatic carbons

Vinyl group carbon (-C)

Hydroxyl group hydrogen

Epoxide carbon

On the basis of ¹³C nuclear magnetic Resonance spectra (NMR) the compounds have aromatic and aliphatic carbon that are identified on the basis of chemical shift value in parts per million (delta). The vinyl hydrogen has different chemical shift value. The methyl group contains primary carbon with

Chemical shift

26-28.3 p. p. m.

22-23.2 ppm

2 3.5-4 ppm

20.1-22.5 ppm

20.3-20.4 ppm

Interpretation

neighboring group effect

splitting of signal

intensity is fast

number of signal

electronic

minimum chemical shift value in parts per million. The epoxide shows different part per million values of chemical shift. The chemical shift value for carbon is twenty times more and the intensity of the compound is four times less as compared to hydrogen nuclear magnetic resonance.

GG-33 (Formononetin)

DEPT (135)

Fig 11: DEPT of Formononetin

Name of atom	Chemical shift	Interpretation
Aromat. deuterium	7-8.4 ppm	neighbor groups effect
Aliphat. Deuterium	2-3.2 ppm	splitting of signal
Vinyl group deuterium	3.5-4 ppm	intensity is fast
Hydroxyl group deuterium	2.1-2.5 ppm	number of signal
Epoxide deuterium	2.3-2.4 ppm	nil
Methyl group	1.2-1.5 ppm	primarydeuterium

On the premise of deuterium atomic attractive spectra (2D NMR) the compound has sweet-smelling and aliphaticdeuterium that are recognized on the premise of synthetic move an incentive in parts for each million. The vinyldeuterium has diverse synthetic move esteem. The methyl amass contains primarydeuterium with least synthetic move an incentive in parts for every million. The epoxide demonstrates diverse part per million estimation of synthetic move (ppm).

GG-33 (Formononetin)

ES-MS

Fig 12: Mass Spectra of Formononetin

According to molecular mass we can determine the molecular weight of the compound. We know that the molecular ion peak present the mass or molecular weight of the unknown compounds. In the given figure the base peak shows the peak at 267.435 that is the mass of the product. The parent peak is known as base or molecular weight of the compound. The fragmentations of the compound shows breaking points and metabolites of the compounds that is very helpful for structure elucidation of the compounds. The m+1, m+2, m+3 etc. Peaks are known as isotopic peak of the compound. These pinnacles are exceptionally useful to decide the sub-atomic formula of the obscure mixes. These two things sub-atomic weight and sub-atomic formula are vital determinant of the auxiliary clarification of the unknown compound. We speak to relative power or wealth on the y-axis and sub-atomic mass on the x-axis for translation. These are very useful for structure elucidation of the unknown compounds.

Biological Assays

Pure Compounds GG-09, GG-47 isolated from *G. glabra* ethanolic extract was evaluated for their *in vitro* biological activities which include: - Antibacterial, Antifungal activity along with original crude.

Agar-Well Diffusion Method for Antimicrobial Screening

Test organisms (Bacteria)

Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)

Vancomycin Resistant *Enterococcus faecalis* (VRE)

Pseudomonas aeruginosa ATCC 27583

Fungal

Candida albicans (FCZ¹)

Aspergillus fumigatus

Assay Media

Bacteria: Muller Hinton agar (Difco, USA)

Fungal: RPMI supplemented with 0.165M MOPS & 1.5% agar (Sigma)

Standard antimicrobial agents used

Ciprofloxacin - 5µg/50µl

Amphotericin B - 1 µg/50µl

Screening of extracts for antimicrobial activity

1. The inoculums were prepared in sterile normal saline of test organisms from the over night growth on trypticase soya broth (for bacteria) & sabouraud dextrose agar (for fungi). For *Aspergillus fumigatus*, used the conidial suspension.

2. Turbidity was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland (equivalent to 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml of *E.coli* & 1×10^6 CFU/ml of *C. albicans*) using a densitometer. 3.500µl of McFarland adjusted cultures was added to 50 ml of sterile molten agar (45 - 50 °C). Muller Hinton agar was used for bacterial cultural & RPMI media for fungal cultures. It was mixed & poured in to PD150 sterile plastic plates. Allowed it to set & then individual plates were marked with the organism inoculated.

1. punched the wells (6 mm diameter) & 50µl of sample (extract) was added to it. Appropriate standard antibiotic was used as a control.

2. Plates was Incubated at 37°C for 24 to 48hrs.

Zone of inhibition was measured & results were recorded.

Table 1: Antibacterial & Antifungal activities of Compounds

S.No.	Tested extracts	Sterility	Tested organisms (Zone Diameter (in mm))				
			Bacterial Pathogens			Fungal Pathogen	
			MRSA	VRE	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C.albicans</i> (FCZ)	<i>A. fumigatus</i>
1.	Crude	NG	0	0	0	0	0
2.	GG-09	NG	4	4	0	2	2
3.	GG - 47	NG	-	-	-	-	-
4.	GG-33	NG	0	0	0	0	0
5.	DMSO control	NG	0	0	0	11 ^H	0
6.	Drug control	NG	0	0	32	20	21

Here H = Hazy zone of inhibition, G = Growth & NG = No Growth. Ciprofloxacin (5µg/well) & Amphotericin-B (1µg/well) were used as a standard antibacterial & antifungal agent respectively in this study.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION OF ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

The Ethanol extract of rhizome of *G. glabra* was chromatographed over silica gel column & then final purification achieved by sephadex (LH-20). compounds, Formononetin (GG-33), Hispaglabridin A (GG-09), Glycyrrazic acid were isolated & their structure was determined by spectroscopic methods.. The major compound Glycyrrhine was hydrolyzed to get aglycone Glycyrrhetic acid.

Compounds were screened for Antibacterial & Antifungal activity, resulted was tabulated in Table 4. However, the crude was not showing any activity (250µg/ml) but pure compounds have different activity pattern against tested organism. None of the compound was found to be active against *P. aeruginosa*.

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